

If you go shopping frequently, here's one thing to worry

Portal Admin

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Apparently, we don't want to see this environmental problem around us (see the photo). At least, our conscience does not allow us to accept it. Nonetheless, we might accidentally become the culprit when going shopping, with our habit of using Single-use plastic (SUP) bags.

Photo. Plastic bags end up in a garbage site.

Our portal's members have recently published a new article concerning SUP bags in December 2024, titled "Intention to use reusable shopping bags in an emerging economy: a Bayesian Mindsponge framework analysis" [1], in Springer's journal *Discover Sustainability*.

The article can be read and downloaded for free from the journal's webpage.

In their concluding remarks, the authors wrote: "However, for the long term strategy, policies on restrictions and gradual bans of the plastic bags in supermarkets and retail stores are of importance on terminating the plastic bags by 2030 in Vietnam". Although it may sound difficult for now, we hope that given increasing evidence from well-grounded studies, like Tran et al. [1], more decisive moves will be made by the authorities and concerned parties such as retailers, producers, and shoppers.

It is noteworthy that the article uses the MCMC computing approach, and BMF analytics [2], and has shown robust estimated results. The results, and their suggestions, offer us some hope for a better vision for ecological sustainability [3].

Congratulations to the authors on this meaningful contribution to the literature.

References

[1] Tran TV, Le MT, Melad AM. (2024). Intention to use reusable shopping bags in an emerging economy: a Bayesian Mindsponge framework analysis. *Discover Sustainability*, **5**, 529. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43621-024-00763-9>

[2] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH, La VP. (Eds.). (2022). *The mindsponge and BMF analytics for innovative thinking in social sciences and humanities*. Walter de Gruyter GmbH.

[3] Nguyen MH. (2024). How can satirical fables offer us a vision for sustainability?. <https://ojs.unito.it/index.php/visions/article/view/11267>

